

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ABSENTEEISM OF PUPILS IN INTERMEDIATE LEVEL AT POBLACION ELEMENTARY SCHOOL INDANAN SOUTH DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study is descriptive-quantitative research determining the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South. Using the weighted mean, the standard deviation, the t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA and Pearson's r correlation test. The study's conclusions are as follows: 1 Of the 100 student respondents, the vast majority are female, between the ages of 11 and 12, and the majority have parents who earned just an elementary education and an average monthly income of 5,000 pesos or less. 2 Sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South by the student-respondents in the context of Physical Factor, Health Factor and Classroom atmosphere is all rated as “neutral” with total weighted mean score of 2.77, 3.43, and 2.67 with standard deviation of 1.07381, 1.00065 and 1.16582 respectively. Additionally Sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism Of Pupils In Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South as perceived by the student-respondents in the context of Personal Attitude, Teacher-Related Factor and Home-Related Factor is all rated as “disagree” with total weighted mean score of 2.4467, 2.2733, 2.3667 with standard deviation of 1.12837, 1.08596, 1.06732 respectively by the student-respondents at Población Elementary School Indanan South Elementary School involved in this study. 3) Generally, there is no significant difference in the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South when data are grouped according to their gender and Parents Average Monthly Income. Meanwhile, student-respondents perceived differently on the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South when data are grouped according to their age and Parents educational attainment.4) Generally, the sub-categories subsumed the extent of Factors Affecting the

Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South is highly correlated.

Keywords: *Absenteeism, Physical Factor, Health Factor, Personal Attitude, Teacher-Related Factor, Classroom Atmosphere; and Home-Related Factor, Descriptive Reseach.*

INTRODUCTION

Being absent from work or school without a valid reason is known as absenteeism. It can be a behavior or a habit. According to the Merriam-Webster definition, absentee students are those who do not consistently attend classes or schools. Additionally, student engagement is impacted by absenteeism. A large number of pupils miss school each day. Lack of perfect discipline both internally and externally is the definition of absenteeism given in the Principle of Education for Teachers in Africa (1995). He gives the impression that the students are unrestrained and do not function within their surroundings. These days, it is impossible to differentiate absence from those who were referred to as pupils. Teasley has found several risk factors that contribute to the high rate of student absenteeism in this country, such as family health, low income, poor school climate, transportation challenges, and community views about education.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the nation's educational system. In private schools during the pandemic, there were an average of 25 million students enrolled, both from government and private schools, according to Belo 2020, the Department of Education. This represents a decrease of 3 million students from the pre-pandemic school year. The US Agency for International Development produced a research in November 2021 that states that during the beginning of the epidemic, the percentage of youth not in school rose from 17% in January 2020 to 25% three months later in April 2020. According to Liego (2016), If a student misses more than 20% of the scheduled classes during the academic year or term, they will receive a failing mark and no credit for the course or subject. Based on the DepEd Manual.

Not only is absence from school concerning to parents, teachers, and administrators, but it also poses a threat to society at large. Unexpected absences negatively impact peer relationships, which in turn may lead to more absences. As stated by (Davidson, Kirt, Wilson, and Malcolm 2003). According to DeSocio et al. (2007), students experience severe academic difficulties and fall far behind in their coursework. According to DeSocio et al. (2007), absenteeism has a negative impact on a student's ability to move on to the following grade and increases the likelihood that they will drop out.

Apart from the negative outcomes associated with student absences, there exist several other factors that also play a role in students' nonattendance. Unrecognized contributing factors to school absenteeism include bad weather and transportation issues.

The pupils might not be able to leave their homes due to severe weather conditions. Health issues are known to be a significant factor in student absenteeism; whether they are personal or family health concerns, they prevent students from attending class. While it is recommended that students avoid attending class when extremely ill, many do not go to school even for minor illnesses that do not interfere with their ability to study in the classroom (DeSocio et al., 2007).

The education system operates under the fundamental premise that pupils attend class on a daily basis. To learn, students need to be attentive and involved. Recent studies, however, have questioned this presumption (Chang, Bauer, & Byrnes, 2018). While some forms of truancy or absences have long been studied, school absenteeism was not regularly measured until recently (U.S. Department of Education, 2016a). The Every Students Succeeds Act (ESSA), which reauthorized federal education law in 2015, pushed states to prioritize student attendance as a reliable indicator of student performance and school quality (SQSS; Jordan & Miller, 2017). Furthermore, as mandated by ESSA, the state must disclose the number of pupils who consistently miss school from their report card. The US Department of Education's Civil Right statistics Collection (CRDC) discovered that about 8 million kids were chronically absent during the 2015–2016 school year, the most recent national statistics available (Chang, Bauer, Byrnes, 2018). Chronically absenteeism is defined as missing 15 or more days of school annually.

Research Questions

This study answered the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Parents Educational attainment; and
 - 1.4 Parents Average Monthly Income?
2. What is the extent of the Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South in terms of:
 - 2.1 Physical Factor;
 - 2.2 Health Factor;
 - 2.3 Personal Attitude;
 - 2.4 Teacher-Related Factor;
 - 2.5 Classroom Atmosphere; and
 - 2.6 Home-Related Factor?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South in terms of: Physical factor, Health factor, Personal attitude, Teacher-related factor, and Classroom atmosphere, Home-related factor; when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Parents Educational Attainment; and

3.4 Parents Average Monthly Income?

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was purely quantitative in nature. The data was analyzed using descriptive techniques. These are used to characterize the variables influencing the absenteeism of intermediate students and the problems faced by the faculty members. They also serve to ascertain whether there are any appreciable differences in the variables influencing the absenteeism of intermediate students based on their age, gender, parent's educational attainment, and parent's monthly income. This was also used to find the link between the subcategories when they were grouped by teacher-related factors, home-related factors, physical factors, health factors, and personal attitudes.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South District - Sulu particularly at intermediate level. It has 8 faculty members and 6 volunteers and it has operated since 2007 with limited resources but had been producing competent graduates.

Respondents of the Study

Since this study was conducted to determine the factors affecting the absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level, therefore the respondents of this study are purely pupils of Poblacion Elementary School particularly from grade 4 to grade 6.

Distribution of respondents according to grade level.

Grade 4	35
Grade 5	25
Grade 6	40
Total	100

Sampling Design

The researcher used the purposive sampling technique to identify and select the 100 participants from the pupils of Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South District. The inclusion criteria was used in choosing the participants of the study in intermediate grades 4-6.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission to the Dean of Graduate Study, after that to the respected advisers of grade 4, grade 5, and grade 6 level as well as the volunteers inside the class who handling the subject during the conduct, especially to the respected teacher in charge of Poblacion Elementary School. Right after the approval, the researcher disseminated the questionnaire to the respondents personally to avoid being bias during the survey. After at least 10 minutes for each respondent, the questionnaires were retrieved.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a standardized questionnaire patterned from Murcia, L (2010, November 15) about the factors affecting the absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level. The questionnaire consists of 2 parts.

Part one (1) deal with the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their age, gender, parent's educational attainment, and parents' average monthly income.

Part two (2) consists the factors affecting the absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School. Their responses are categorized using the Likert scale to make it more convenient to answer and interpret.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical treatment of data includes descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and correlation analysis.

1. For problem number 1, the statistical tools used are frequency and percentage to determine the demographic profile of pupils in terms of age, gender, parent educational attainment and parent's average monthly income.
2. For problem number 2, the statistical tools used are mean, and standard deviation employed to identify the factors affecting the absenteeism of the pupils in intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South District.
3. For problem number 3, the statistical tools used are t-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant difference in the extend of factors affecting the absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School Indanan South when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: age, gender, parents' educational attainment and parents average monthly income.
4. For problem number 4, the statistical tools used are Pearson Product-Moment Correlation to determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under factors affecting the absenteeism of pupils in intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: 1.1 Age, 1.2 Gender, 1.3 Parents educational attainment; and 1.4 Parents Average Monthly Income?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the age distribution of the student respondents' demographic profile. From the table, it is evident that 45 (45.0%) of the 100 student respondents are between the ages of 10 and under, 50 (50.0%) are between the ages of 11 and 12, and 5 (5.0%) are 13 years of age and up. Half of all the student responders in this study are between the ages of 11 and 12, according to the findings. This further suggests that the majority of the study's student respondents fall into the middle age range as defined by the study.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South in terms of age.

Age	Number of respondents	Percent
10 years old and below	45	45.0%
11-12 years old	50	50.0%
13 years old and above	5	5.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 demonstrates the gender-specific demographic profile of the student respondents. This table indicates that 40 (40.0%) of the 100 student responses are male and 60 (60.0%) are female. This survey shows that there are more than half as many female student respondents as there are male student respondents. This means that great majority of the student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South are predominantly female.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of respondents	Percent
Male	40	40.0%
Female	60	60.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Parents educational attainment

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of Parents educational attainment. It can be seen from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 57 (57.0%) have parents who are Elementary graduate, 13 (13.0%) are high school graduate, 22 (22.0%) are college graduate, and 8 (8.0%) others. This study reveals that more than half of the total number of student-respondents' parents are elementary graduate. This implies that a significant portion of the parents' educational attainment of the student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South have attained a lower level of education, with the majority being elementary graduates.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South in terms of Parents educational attainment.

Parents educational attainment	Number of respondents	Percent
Elementary Graduate	57	57.0%
High School Graduate	13	13.0%
College Graduate	22	22.0%
Others	8	8.0%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Parents Average Monthly income

Table 1.4 shows the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of Parents Average Monthly Income. It can be seen from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 87 (87.0%) have 5,000 below average monthly income of parents, 12 (12.0%) have 5,001-10,000, and 1 (1.0%) have 10,001 above. This study shows that more than half of the total number of student-respondents have an average of 5,000 pesos and below of their parents' monthly income. This result implies that a large majority of the student-respondents come from families with relatively low average monthly incomes. Specifically, this indicates that many families may face financial constraints and challenges in meeting basic needs and expenses.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile of student-respondents from Población Elementary School Indanan South in terms of Parents Average Monthly Income.

Parents Average Monthly Income	Number of respondents	Percent
5,000 below	87	87.0%
5,001-10,000	12	12.0%
10,001 above	1	1.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Intermediate pupils at Poblacion Elementary School in terms of: 2.1 Physical Factor, 2.2 Health Factor, 2.3 Personal Attitude, 2.4 Teacher-Related Factor, 2.5 Classroom Atmosphere; and 2.6 Home-Related Factor?

2.1 In the context of Physical Factor

Table 2.1 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Physical Factor. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.77 with standard deviation of 1.07381 which is rated as “Neutral”. This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed that there is a Neutral effect on their Absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Physical Factor. This implies that the students perceive the physical factors as having neither a significant positive nor negative impact on their absenteeism.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items as “**Neutral**”: “Our house is far from the school.”, and “Nobody accompanies me in going to school”.

Table 2.1 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Physical Factor.

Statements	Mean	S.D	Rating
1 Our house is far from the school.	3.26	1.685	Neutral
2 It is unsafe to go to school.	2.28	1.415	Disagree
3 Nobody accompanies me in going to school.	2.77	1.626	Neutral
Total Weighted Mean	2.77	1.07381	Neutral

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.2 In the context of Health Factor

Table 2.2 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Health Factor. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 3.43 with standard deviation of 1.00065 which is rated as “Neutral”. This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed that there is a Neutral effect on their Absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Health factor. This implies that students perceive health-related factors as having neither a significant positive nor negative impact on their absenteeism.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items, among others as “**Neutral**”: “I have toothache.”, “My stomach hurts”, and “I have headache.”

Table 2.2 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Health factor.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 I have toothache	3.38	1.455	Neutral
2 My stomach hurts.	3.45	1.473	Neutral
3 I have headache.	3.45	1.520	Neutral
Total Weighted Mean	3.43	1.00065	Neutral

2.3 In the context of Personal attitude

Table 2.3 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of personal attitude. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.45 with standard deviation of 1.12837 which is rated as “Disagree”. This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed they do not perceive to have a significant effect on their absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of personal attitude.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items, among others as “**Disagree**”: “I cannot concentrate in my studies.”, and “I got fond of playing game with my cellphone.”

Table 2.3 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of personal attitude.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 I’m not interested in my studies.	2.56	1.585	Neutral
2 I cannot concentrate in my studies.	2.47	1.417	Disagree
3 I got fond of playing game with my cellphone.	2.31	1.549	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean	2.45	1.12837	Disagree

2.4 In the context of Teacher-related factor

Table 2.4 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Teacher-related factor. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.27 with standard deviation of 1.08596 which is rated as “Disagree”. This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed that they do not perceive to have a significant effect on their absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Teacher-related factor.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items, among others as “Disagree”: “My teacher scolds me.”, “I cannot understand my teacher’ lesson.”, and, “I do not like my teacher.”

Table 2.4 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Teacher-Related Factor

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 My teacher scolds me.	2.39	1.456	Disagree
2 I cannot understand my teacher’ lesson.	2.23	1.392	Disagree
3 I do not like my teacher.	2.20	1.449	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean	2.27	1.08596	Disagree

2.5 In the context of Classroom Atmosphere

Table 2.5 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan in the context of Classroom Atmosphere. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.67 with standard deviation of 1.16582 which is rated as “Neutral”. This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed that there is a Neutral effect on their Absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Classroom Atmosphere. This implies that students perceive factors as having neither a significant positive nor negative impact on their absenteeism.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items, among others as “Neutral”: “Our classroom is hot and uncomfortable.”, and “It is noisy inside the classroom.”

Table 2.5 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Classroom Atmosphere.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 Our classroom is hot and uncomfortable.	2.78	1.474	Neutral
2 It is noisy inside the classroom.	2.91	1.688	Neutral
3 A classmate/classmate's bullies/bully me.	2.32	1.582	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean	2.67	1.16582	Neutral

2.6 In the context of Home-Related Factor

Table 2.6 shows the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective in the context of Home-Related Factor. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.37 with standard deviation of 1.06732 which is rated as "Disagree". This result indicates that the students involved in this study affirmed that they do not perceive to have a significant effect on their absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South the context of Home-Related Factor.

Notably, student-respondents rated the following items, among others as "Disagree": "My parents quarreled", and "I have no money to buy snacks in school."

Table 2.6 Extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Home-Related Factor.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 My parents quarreled	2.43	1.486	Disagree
2 I am too pre-occupied with household chores.	2.54	1.520	Neutral
3 I have no money to buy snacks in school.	2.13	1.447	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean	2.37	1.06732	Disagree

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School in terms of: Physical factor, Health factor, Personal attitude, Teacher-related factor, Classroom atmosphere, Home-related factor; when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: 3.1 Age, 3.2 Gender, 3.3 Parents Parents educational attainment, and 3.4 Parents Average Monthly Income?

3.1 According to Age

Table 3.1 shows the variation in the degree of factors influencing the absenteeism of students in Población Elementary School's Intermediate level when data are categorized based on their age-related demographic profile. The F-values and probability values of the subcategories that are subsumed are in fact significant at alpha 0.05, as this table illustrates. This indicates that although the respondents were primary school students, their ages varied, but generally speaking, so did their perceptions of the factors behind their absence from Población primary's intermediate level. This implies that student-respondents with the age range 13 years old and above may make him/her better perceiver toward extent of impact of preschool program in the case of Población Elementary School Indanan South compared to those within 10 years old and below as categorized in this study, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has indeed significant intervention in the ways how student-respondents at Población Elementary School Indanan South perceive the extent of impact of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: "There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age" is rejected.

Table 3.1 Difference in the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
	Between Groups	25.468	2	12.734	13.928	.000	Significant
		88.686	97	.914			
Physical Factor	Within Groups	114.154	99				
	Total						

Health Factor	Between Groups	5.100	2	2.550	2.631	.077	Not Significant
		94.029	97	.969			
	Within Groups	99.129	99				
	Total						
Personal Attitude	Between Groups	39.982	2	19.991	22.531	.000	Significant
		86.066	97	.887			
	Within Groups	126.049	99				
	Total						
Teacher-Related Factor	Between Groups	51.929	2	25.965	38.854	.000	Significant
		64.822	97	.668			
	Within Groups	116.751	99				
	Total						
Classroom Atmosphere	Between Groups	26.716	2	13.358	12.016	.000	Significant
		107.838	97	1.112			
	Within Groups	134.554	99				
	Total						
Home-Related Factor	Between Groups	29.480	2	14.740	17.165	.000	Significant
		83.298	97	.859			
	Within Groups	112.778	99				
	Total						

* Significant at alpha 0.05

When data are grouped according to client-respondents' demographic profile in terms of average monthly family income, a Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test is performed to determine which groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary.

Table 3.1.1 shows the multiple comparison of the subcategories subsumed under extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población

Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age. It reveals on this study that student-respondents who are 10 years and below tend to perceive better on the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary compared to those middle and upper level of age group as categorized in this study.

Table 3.1.1 Multiple comparison of the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their Demographic profile in terms of age.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
On Physical Factor	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	.99259*	.19648	.000
		13 years old and above	1.19259*	.45075	.026
Personal Attitude	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	1.29407*	.19355	.000
		13 years old and above	.94074	.44404	.091
Teacher-Related Factor	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	1.47926*	.16798	.000
		13 years old and above	.92593*	.38536	.047
Classroom Atmosphere	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	1.00370*	.21666	.000
		13 years old and above	1.30370*	.49704	.027
Home-Related Factor	10 years old and below	11-12 years old	-1.30370*	.49704	.027
		13 years old and above	-.30000	.49455	.817

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.2 According to Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School when data

are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. As this table illustrates, when data are grouped according to their gender-specific demographic profile at Población Elementary School, all of the F-values and probability values of the subcategories covered under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level are not significant at alpha 0.05, with the exception of the Health Factor. This indicates that there is no difference in the perceptions of male and female student respondents regarding the factors influencing the level of absenteeism among intermediate-level students at Población Elementary School Indanan South. This further suggests that when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, or vice versa, being a male student-respondent may not make him a better perceiver toward the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant intervention in the ways how student-respondents at Población Elementary School Indanan perceive the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender” is rejected.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Physical Factor	Male	2.8917	1.12568	.20278	.924	.358	Not Significant
	Female	2.6889	1.03946				
Health Factor	Male	3.7000	.91147	.45556	.20007	.025	Not Significant
	Female	3.2444	1.02302				
Personal Attitude	Male	2.5000	.97548	.08889	.23133	.702	Not Significant
	Female	2.4111	1.22646				

Teacher-Related Factor	Male	2.3500	1.10670	.12778	.574	.567	Not Significant
	Female	2.2222	1.07823				
Classroom Atmosphere	Male	2.6000	1.21294	-.11667	.23889	.626	Not Significant
	Female	2.7167	1.14129				
Home-Related Factor	Male	2.4833	1.13968	.19444	.21809	.375	Not Significant
	Female	2.2889	1.01860				

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 According to Parents educational attainment

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Parents educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that except for Physical factor and health factor, all the F-values and probability values of the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education –Sulu are indeed significant at alpha 0.05. This means that though the student-respondents involved in this study vary in their Parents educational attainment, generally they differ in their perceptions toward the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School. It implies that the parents of student-respondents with doctorate degree may be a better perceiver on the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South District compared to those who only have bachelor's degree as their parents' educational attainment.

Hence, it is safe to say that generally, the Parents educational attainment variable has a significant intervention in the ways how student-respondents perceive the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: "There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Población Elementary School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Parents educational attainment" is rejected.

Table 3.3 Difference in the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Parents educational attainment.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Physical Factor	Between Groups	6.524	3	2.175	1.940	.128	Not Significant
	Within Groups	107.631	96	1.121			
	Between Groups	114.154	99				
	Total						
Health Factor	Between Groups	2.418	3	.806	.800	.497	Not Significant
	Within Groups	96.711	96				
	Between Groups	99.129	99	1.007			
	Total						
Personal Attitude	Between Groups	25.422	3	8.474	8.084	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	100.627	96				
	Between Groups	126.049	99	1.048			
	Total						
Teacher-Related Factor	Between Groups	15.461	3	5.154	4.885	.003	Significant
	Within Groups	101.290	96				
	Between Groups	116.751	99	1.055			
	Total						
Classroom Atmosphere	Between Groups	20.153	3	6.718	5.637	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	114.402	96				
	Between Groups	134.554	99				
	Total			1.192			

Home-Related Factor	Between Groups	11.655	3	3.885	3.688	.015	Significant
		101.123	96				
	Within Groups	112.778	99	1.053			
	Total						

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.4 According to Parents Average Monthly Income

Table 3.4 shows the variation in the degree of factors influencing the absenteeism of students in Población Elementary School's Intermediate level when data are grouped based on their demographic profile, specifically their parents' average monthly income. This table shows that all of the F-values and probability values of the subcategories that are included are not significant at alpha 0.05, with the exception of the Health Factor. This indicates that while the study's participant students' parents' average monthly income varies, their assessments of the factors influencing intermediate students' absenteeism at Población Elementary School generally do not differ. It suggests that student respondents who reported a monthly income of 5000 pesos or less than their parents may not have had a better understanding of the factors influencing students' absenteeism at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the intermediate level than respondents who reported a monthly income of 10001 or more.

Hence, it is safe to say that the Parents Average Monthly Income variable has no significant intervention in the ways how preschool student-respondents perceive the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: "There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Población Elementary School Indanan South elementary school when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Parents Average Monthly Income" is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of Factors Affecting their Absenteeism in Intermediate level at Población Elementary when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Parents Average Monthly Income.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Physical Factor	Between Groups	5.635	2	2.817	2.518	.086	Not Significant
		108.520	97	1.119			
	Within Groups	114.154	99				

	Total						
Health Factor	Between Groups	7.168	2	3.584	3.780	.026	Significant
	Within Groups	91.961	97	.948			
	Total						
Personal Attitude	Between Groups	2.642	2	1.321	1.038	.358	Not Significant
	Within Groups	123.407	97	1.272			
	Total						
Teacher-Related Factor	Between Groups	.999	2	.500	.419	.659	Not Significant
	Within Groups	115.752	97	1.193			
	Total						
Classroom Atmosphere	Between Groups	3.479	2	1.740	1.287	.281	Not Significant
	Within Groups	131.075	97	1.351			
	Total						
Home-Related Factor	Between Groups	.819	2	.409	.355	.702	Not Significant
	Within Groups	111.959	97	1.154			
	Total						

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories under Factor Affecting the Absenteeism of pupils in Intermediate level at Poblacion Elementary School?

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level At Población

Elementary School Indanan South. As shown in the table, the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05.

Furthermore, the correlational degree among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South is as follows:

- 1) Low positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Physical Factor, Health Factor and Home-Related Factor.
- 2) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Physical Factor, Personal Attitude and Classroom Atmosphere. It implies that these factors play significant roles in influencing pupil absenteeism at the school, suggesting that addressing these factors may be crucial in reducing absenteeism.
- 3) Nearly Zero positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Health Factor, Teacher-Related Factor and Home-Related Factor.
- 4) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Health Factor and Personal Attitude.
- 5) Low positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of classroom atmosphere and health factor.
- 6) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils In Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Personal Attitude, Teacher-Related Factor, Classroom Atmosphere and Home-Related Factor.
- 7) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils In Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Teacher-Related Factor, Classroom Atmosphere and Home-Related Factor.

High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils In Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South in the context of Classroom Atmosphere and Home-Related Factor.

This study reveals various degrees of correlation among factors affecting absenteeism of intermediate-level pupils at Población Elementary School Indanan South. Firstly, there's a low positive correlation between Physical Factor, Health Factor, and Home-Related Factor, suggesting a weak relationship among these factors and absenteeism. Secondly, a high positive correlation between Physical Factor, Personal Attitude, and Classroom Atmosphere indicates significant roles these factors play in absenteeism, suggesting addressing them could reduce absenteeism. Thirdly, a nearly

zero positive correlation between Health Factor, Teacher-Related Factor, and Home-Related Factor implies minimal influence on absenteeism. Furthermore, a high positive correlation between Health Factor and Personal Attitude indicates their substantial impact on absenteeism. Additionally, a low positive correlation between classroom atmosphere and health factor suggests a weaker connection. Furthermore, a high positive correlation among Personal Attitude, Teacher-Related Factor, Classroom Atmosphere, and Home-Related Factor emphasizes their collective influence on absenteeism. Lastly, high positive correlations among Teacher-Related Factor, Classroom Atmosphere, and Home-Related Factor or between Classroom Atmosphere and Home-Related Factor highlight their significant combined effect on absenteeism.

Hence, it is safe to say that generally the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South are highly correlated. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils In Intermediate Level At Población Elementary School Indanan South” is rejected.

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Factors Affecting the Absenteeism of Pupils in Intermediate Level at Población Elementary School Indanan South.

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Physical Factor	Health Factor	.233*	.020	100	Low
	Personal Attitude	.558**	.000	100	High
	Teacher- Related Factor	.486**	.000	100	Moderate
	Classroom Atmosphere	.549**	.000	100	High
	Home- Related Factor	.260**	.000	100	Low
Health Factor	Personal Attitude	-.003	.980	100	High

	Teacher-Related Factor	.013	.894	100	Nearly Zero
	Classroom Atmosphere	.159	.113	100	Low
	Home-Related Factor	.065	.518	100	Nearly Zero
	Teacher-Related Factor	.628**	.000	100	High
Personal Attitude	Classroom Atmosphere	.641**	.000	100	High
	Home-Related Factor	.504**	.000	100	High
	Classroom Atmosphere	.625**	.000	100	High
Teacher-Related Factor	Home-Related Factor	.624**	.000	100	High
Classroom Atmosphere	Home-Related Factor	.511**	.000	100	High

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect.

Conclusions

The study concludes the following:

1) The demographic profile of student-respondents in the Población Elementary School Indanan South is characterized by a predominance of females. Additionally, a substantial majority falls within the age group of 11-12 years old of age brackets. Furthermore, majority of student-respondents have parents who are a graduate of elementary earning an average of not more than 5000 incomes per month. These findings

2) This here findings suggest that while student-respondents perceive the factors related to absenteeism differently across various contexts, there is a tendency to disagree regarding the influence of Personal Attitude, Teacher-Related Factor, and Home-Related Factor on absenteeism among intermediate-level pupils at Población Elementary School Indanan South.

3) Generally, the analysis suggests that there is no substantial difference in the extent of factors affecting absenteeism among intermediate-level pupils at Población Elementary School Indanan South when data are grouped by gender and parents' average monthly income. However, when grouped by age and parents' educational attainment, there are differing perceptions among student-respondents regarding the extent of these factors. This indicates that age and parents' educational attainment may influence how students perceive the factors contributing to absenteeism, whereas gender and parents' average monthly income may not have as significant an impact on these perceptions.

4) The analysis indicates a high degree of correlation among the sub-categories encompassing the extent of factors influencing absenteeism among intermediate-level pupils at Población Elementary School Indanan South. This suggests a strong interconnection among these factors, indicating that they collectively contribute to the phenomenon of absenteeism.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1) Department of Education (DepEd) may establish mechanisms for ongoing monitoring and evaluation of absenteeism rates and intervention effectiveness. DepEd may provide guidance on data collection methods, performance indicators, and evaluation frameworks to ensure rigorous monitoring and assessment of intervention outcomes.

2) Teachers in the Población Elementary School Indanan South may prioritize their own professional development and growth to stay abreast of current research, best practices, and emerging trends in education. Teachers can stay inspired and motivated in their practice, improve their teaching skills, and broaden their knowledge base by participating in professional learning groups, workshops, and ongoing training. Additionally, discuss with the parents the advantages of having their kids in school whenever there are classes during the parent-teacher conference. Stress that if they continue to ask their kids to miss school, it will create a negative example for the kids.

3) Educators are encouraged to actively participate in conducting a thorough assessment of all factors contributing to absenteeism, considering their interconnections and collective impact. This should involve taking a comprehensive look at the individual, physical, health, and teacher-related aspects as well as the classroom and home environments. Teach the pupils how to look after their general health. Oral health and general sickness should be prioritized.

4) More so, Future researchers in the field of Education are encouraged to conduct study like this one to further assess the factors contributing to absenteeism among

intermediate-level pupils and how will it affect their academic performance, socio-emotional development, and overall well-being.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

First, a comprehensive informed consent form explaining the goals, methods, potential risks and benefits, and confidentiality policies was delivered to each participant. Furthermore, all trial data points were carefully anonymised in cases when the respondents' personal information had no bearing on the trial results. Data collection was conducted in a private environment to preserve participant privacy, and the collected data was kept in a secure archive that was only accessible by the researchers. Despite the differences in their thoughts and points of view, all members were respected in the same spirit. Additionally, the researchers made an effort to give the participants a welcoming and secure environment so they could talk openly about their experiences.

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